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Assessment of digital platforms for the quantification of co-benefits in nature-based solutions

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Abstract

The significance of Nature-Based Solutions (NBSs) in addressing environmental and socioeconomic challenges is widely acknowledged, yet research on NBSs continues due to a limited understanding of their full benefits. This study addresses the existing gap by focusing on NBS co-benefit valuation through digital platforms. These platforms support NBSs by assessing their effectiveness, contributing to SDGs, enabling data collection, analysis, and stakeholder engagement. The paper identifies platforms for co-benefit quantification, encompassing public health, climate change, water management, air quality, biodiversity, soil management, and socioeconomic values. Some of these platforms, like InVEST, ARIES, and i-Tree-Eco offer multiple models to quantify various benefits of NBS. FreeStation is a platform to capture environmental data in a near real-time-basis, and Co\$tingNature is a platform providing global data to estimate the contribution of nature to sustainable development goals (SDGs). However, most platforms focus on limited areas, so combining data from multiple platforms is necessary for holistic NBS co-benefit quantification.

KEYWORDS

co-benefit quantification, digital platforms, environment, nature-based solutions, NBS, socioeconomic

1 | INTRODUCTION

The increasing importance of ecosystem-based strategies to address environmental, social, and economic issues is necessitating the quantification of ecosystem services (Faivre et al., 2017). While our ecosystems are rapidly deteriorating, (Smith et al., 2019; Turney et al., 2020), it is pertinent to develop effective tools and strategies to address regional and global challenges to protect our environment (Malekmohammadi & Mirbagheri, 2023; Seddon et al., 2021). In this context, Nature-based Solutions (NBSs) which are linked to concepts of sustainable development, can play a critical role in preserving the planet's natural ecosystems (Thompson et al., 2023) whilst providing

environmental, social, and economic co-benefits. Co-benefits are the positive effects that a measure aimed at one objective might have on other objectives (IPCC, 2014).

NBSs are solutions to protect, conserve, restore, sustainably use and manage ecosystems. These solutions address social, economic, and environmental challenges effectively and adaptively, while also enhancing human well-being, providing ecosystem services, and boosting resilience and biodiversity. (United Nations Environment Assembly-UNEA, 2020). NBS incorporates concepts like ecological engineering, blue-green infrastructure, ecosystem-based adaptation, etc., offering a transdisciplinary, collaborative and holistic approach for designing and implementing 'win-win solutions' (El Harrak &

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Lemaitre, 2023). In Europe, policymakers have integrated NBS in the European Green Deal, the Biodiversity Strategy, Climate Adaptation Strategy, and more, as NBS can not only address immediate needs but offer long-term solutions to complex problems like sea-level rise (Seddon et al., 2020). Moreover, NBS can significantly contribute to several SDGs by promoting the delivery of multiple ecosystem services, resulting in various co-benefits including sustainable economy (Gómez Martín et al., 2020; Shao et al., 2024). However, to fully realize the potential of the contribution, it is necessary to share co-benefits, report and monitor progress, and provide constructive inputs to refine existing policies (Dhyani et al., 2023). Despite the increasing use of NBS, limited monitoring of NBS' impacts has enabled greenwashing and unequal distribution of NBS' benefits, leading to lack of consensus on its transformational capacity (El Harrak & Lemaitre, 2023). As NBS are incorporated within important EU policies, it is timely and pertinent to coordinate knowledge development for better quantification and monitoring of NBS, in order to ensure its effectiveness and prevent greenwashing (El Harrak & Lemaitre, 2023). On the other hand, the expected impact of co-benefits is conveyed only in qualitative terms as their measurement continues to be a major challenge in NBS research. Quantification is crucial for assessing the importance of the potential impact of side effects as well as the sustainability of NBS in light of their contributions to other societal challenges (Ommer et al., 2022).

Key challenges in the valuation of ecosystem services include irreversibility and high levels of uncertainty (Zandebasiri et al., 2023). Other challenges include: (i) the time-consuming and resource-intensive process of collecting primary data, which often requires extensive fieldwork and sampling, (ii) difficulty finding reliable secondary data, which can be outdated, incomplete, or collected using different methodologies compared to primary data, making it less suited for accurate valuations (Johnston, 2014), (iii) lack of access to public sector records, (iv) difficulty quantifying intangible benefits such as esthetic appeal, (v) difficulty finding the correct sample size and engage participants for surveys/interviews, (vi) lacking enough evidence of the utility of NBS due to limited monitoring of NBS, (vii) extremely interdisciplinary work requiring a range of skills and interaction among various stakeholders (Aghimien et al., 2024), (viii) limited NBS projects available to study and more (Nelson et al., 2020). A digital platform for NBS provides evidence-based baselines to researchers and policy analysts who are interested in contextualizing climate action plans to local communities and address these challenges. When the economic and environmental benefits of NBS are identified, producers, especially new investors, are encouraged to adopt these solutions (Chishti et al., 2021). These platforms can also facilitate integration between ecological, technology and social components of NBS implementations (Wellmann et al., 2023). Traditionally researchers or scientists had to perform field observations and sample collections which was usually resource intensive, time-consuming, and an expensive way of data collection. However, with the use of digital platforms, researchers can perform remote data collection in less time and half the cost. NBS indicators of its benefits can be collected using digital platforms, and researchers can observe

the patterns of their datasets, remotely, by simply inspecting the values collected on the application (Kabisch et al., 2016). Digital platform can also be architected to acquire data from multiple sources, for example, Remotely Sensed satellite imagery, GPS, Sensors, mobile app questionnaire and other secondary datasets can be made available via a centralized data repository. The availability of comprehensive ecological and social datasets makes a digital platform ideal for strategizing tailored NBS interventions (Wellmann et al., 2023). Digital platforms for NBS can serve as decision-making tool (Frantzeskaki et al., 2019), when the computational logic or mathematical approaches are programmed create baseline models using source datasets. However, determining the most suitable platforms for monitoring or quantifying co-benefits of NBSs can be challenging, given the numerous options available and diverse groups of stakeholders (Thompson et al., 2017). Although some studies have addressed this aim by suggesting toolkits and platforms, they primarily focused on quantifying co-benefits in specific contexts such as green infrastructure (Alvarado et al., 2019), urban NBS (Van Oijstaeijen et al., 2020), and Marine Ecosystems (Qu et al., 2021). Recent literature has introduced and reviewed frameworks to quantify NBS co-benefits (Epelde et al., 2022; Mirbagheri et al., 2017; Kumar et al., 2021; Viti et al., 2022; Watkin et al., 2019). However, while these studies have explored the theoretical foundations and individual case studies of NBS, there is a distinct lack of research focused on practical tools that can streamline and enhance the monitoring and evaluation processes.

This study aims to fill this gap by providing a thorough assessment of digital platforms. Specifically, it seeks to answer the question “What are the open access digital platforms that effectively quantify co-benefits of NBS?” by considering the following objectives:

1. Identify open-access platforms that quantify at least one co-benefit of NBSs applicable across Europe.
2. Evaluate the capabilities of the selected platforms for assessing the co-benefits of NBSs and determining if they can perform economic valuation.
3. Identify crucial capability gaps and potential opportunities for future development in this field.

2 | METHODS

2.1 | Platform identification

Evaluating the effectiveness of NBSs can be assessed with quantifying or monitoring of their co-benefits. The co-benefit refers to the advantages and services provided by and nature through the environmental and social, and economic aspects of sustainability (Balzan et al., 2022). In this paper, we divided these co-benefits to seven categories: (i) Public health and well-being; (ii) Climate change; (iii) water management and quality; (iv) Air quality and temperature cooling; (v) Biodiversity; (vi) Soil management; (vii) social values, tourism, esthetic appeal, and recreation. (Socioeconomic values).

FIGURE 1 Flowchart representing the methodology.

We conducted a web search (from June to October 2023) through web of science and using various Google search engine (to include gray literature), to identify relevant platforms. The flowchart depicted in Figure 1 illustrates the steps for choosing these platforms. Each search term was constructed by combining keywords from co-benefit categories (e.g., for co-benefits related to climate change: ‘platform’, ‘tool’, ‘valuate’, ‘quantify’, ‘carbon storage’ or ‘carbon sequestration’). From the beginning, only open-access platforms were chosen. Mobile applications were not considered. Additionally, we supplemented the searches by including terms such as ‘ecosystem services’ and ‘Nature-based Solutions’ to broaden the scope and identify more relevant platforms. In the process of identifying platforms for this review, we made a distinction between digital platforms or platforms, independent datasets, mathematical models, and instructional resources. This categorization helped us narrow the research scope and emphasis on platforms that enable the calculation of co-benefits associated with NBSs.

We excluded mathematical models which are included in scientific resources because they are often tailored to specific case studies and can be challenging to replicate. Additionally, guidance materials like tools with PDF or Excell files were not included as they do not directly enable the quantification of co-benefit categories. Independent datasets were excluded from consideration since they are outcomes and do not represent implementations of applied methods. For this review, the term “platform” refers specifically to software and

tools that enable access to digital executions of models or functionalities, providing the monitoring and quantification of co-benefits related to NBSs. More over, platforms were not considered where sufficient information or supported literature could not be found. We thoroughly screened the platforms to ensure that, they either include or enable users to provide the necessary supporting datasets for their application; and they are appropriate for European applications or can be readily used without huge parameterization. It was imperative to provide a detailed summary of the excluded platforms that are effective in enhancing resilience through NBS implementation, as well. Hence, section ‘Stakeholder Engagement Platforms’ was included.

2.2 | Platform evaluation

The evaluation of selected platforms involved technical evaluation, co-benefit categories assessment, strengths-constraints analysis, and alternative methods exploration. Technical evaluation is the heart of the evaluation involved a deep dive into the technical aspects of the platforms. Technical manuals, scientific literatures, and online information from platform websites were analyzed to assess the platforms’ capabilities comprehensively. This included an examination of the methodologies used, an overview of key quantified results, and the consideration of economic measures where applicable. In the assessment of co-benefit categories, each category for the selected

platforms was thoroughly examined. This involved presenting a concise description of the methodology employed for each category and outlining the platforms' functionality for valuation. Importantly, this step illuminated the extent to which the platforms could measure and monitor NBS co-benefits. Beyond the technical aspects, the evaluation also considered the strengths and constraints of the platforms. An overview of these aspects was provided, giving stakeholders a well-rounded view of what each platform excelled at and where it might have limitations. Acknowledging the dynamic nature of the digital platform landscape, the methodology also explored alternative methods found within the scientific literature. This served to complement the evaluation by presenting potential alternatives for assessing NBS co-benefits. In essence, the methodology adopted for this evaluation was meticulous, rigorous, and focused on providing stakeholders with a comprehensive understanding of the capabilities, strengths, and potential limitations of digital platforms for quantifying NBS co-benefits.

The effectiveness of digital platforms is contingent on the quality and availability of data. Despite using Google search, the study might have encountered limitations due to inconsistent or incomplete data reported in the literature. Additionally, the platforms reviewed may have technological or geographic constraints, limiting their applicability in different contexts or regions. To mitigate this, we limited the scope of the platforms to include only those applicable to Europe; however, this review might still not fully address these contextual limitations.

3 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A total of 12 platforms were listed after fulfilling the necessary criteria (Table 1). The description, comparison, and evaluation of these platforms are discussed within the related co-benefit categories. The method behind each platform is also provided in Tables 2–8. Additionally, the platforms' contributions to 17 SDGs are provided, specifying their respective goals (for more information about related SDGs see Table S1). Their web links are listed in Table S2, for access to each platform. Water management and climate change were the most assessed aspects related to NBS co-benefits. While socioeconomic benefits of NBSs are important, there were limited platforms to value those benefits. The main reason is that intangible socio-cultural services require some methods like interviewing the community to assess their willingness to pay through choice-modeling. In other hands, as stockholder engagement is a major factor for well-implemented NBS, the most widely used platforms in this regard were selected from excluded ones and listed in Table S3. These platforms play a crucial role in enhancing community resilience and they can contribute to SDG 17, “Partnerships to achieve the Goal.”

3.1 | Public health and well-being

The public health and well-being co-benefits are modeled by the three platforms listed in Table 2. Among these, BenMap has distinctive

functionalities to model scenarios and evaluate the benefits of improved air quality on human health. The possibility to compute the economic value of health impacts in terms of the “Cost of illness” and an individual's “Willingness to Pay” for hospital admissions makes the tool best suited to NBS feasibility studies and evidence-based policy formulations. BenMap interpolates air pollutant concentrations (PM 2.5 or Ozone levels), Population datasets, Health incidence rates or mortality rates data to estimate the impact of air pollution on Human Health (Fann et al., 2009). The software uses a risk estimate function to perform the cost–benefit analysis and simulate the Health and Economic impacts. The input datasets can be at different locational scales or spatial resolutions, while census population data at a county-state-national level, and health or mortality rates at a county-state-national level (Sacks et al., 2018). However, the station-wise air pollution grids are the spatial baseline for which health or economic estimates will be computed. The tool, renowned for its evidence-based monitoring or prediction capabilities, is widely used among policy analysts and epidemiology researchers to understand air pollutant concentration trends and changes in health/disease incidences before and after a policy intervention (Sacks et al., 2018). BenMap allows users to upload custom datasets for any location across the world. The other platform, AccessMod, shows the accessibility to healthcare facilities (Ray & Ebner, 2008). The travel time analysis is used to model the time taken to access the nearest healthcare facility and the exposure to hazards or proximity to de-forested areas (Poirier et al., 2021).

AccessMod is a geographic and data analytics toolkit developed by World Health Organization (WHO) (Ray & Ebner, 2008). Evaluation of Health service coverage through the layers of the target population, availability coverage, and accessibility coverage (Tanahashi, 1978) is critical to assess “Public Health and well-being” (SDG 3) NBS co-benefit of a community. AccessMod performs the evaluation by considering factors of digital elevation or slope, land cover, road networks, and rivers/wetlands as barriers to mobility. When combined with the existing facilities layer (provided by the toolkit), the merged land cover layer and population statistics can help analyze the accessibility, geographic coverage, referral facilities, or zonal statistics of the location. Many policy reforms and urban infrastructure planning (SDG 11) to Improve emergency obstetric and newborn care (EmONC) have been performed using the tool (Kogi, 2016). Nevertheless, AccessMod has limited visualization capacities; outputs need to be exported to GIS (Geographic Information System) software or spreadsheets to perform economic evaluations or visualize results. Furthermore, AtlasPlus is an online application offering geo-spatial and tabular visualizations of Social Determinants of Health (SDH) and health incidents (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, CDC, 2023). SDH includes five indicators: poverty, uninsured, less than a high school education and vacant housing; percentage of population living in rural areas (nationally and by state); and county urbanization level. Users can compare social determinants such as poverty rates, income, education levels, housing, urbanization, and physician rates to specific diseases. While AtlasPlus focuses on North American datasets, it serves as a valuable framework for visualizing public health indicators,

TABLE 1 Selected platforms that quantify at least one co-benefit of NBSs.

No	Name	Type	Description	Co-benefit outputs	SDGs	example of references
1	AccessMod	Desktop-Application	WHO tool to visualize access to healthcare facilities based on disease types	Public health/ well-being	3	(Poirier et al., 2021)
2	ARIES	Web-application/ k.LAB Integrated Modelling	An artificial intelligent modeller, from a single model or a collection of models	Climate change; Water management; Soil management; Social values	11 6 13 15	(Bagstad et al., 2011)
3	AtlastPlus	GIS- ICT/ Web-Application	An epidemiological surveillance platform displaying spatial trends and temporal changes in surveillance data for diseases.	Public health/ well-being	3	(Kim Elmore, 2017)
4	BenMAP	Desktop-Application	Assess the health and economic benefits of improved Air Quality	Public health/ well-being; Air quality	3	(Fann et al., 2009)
5	Co\$tingNature	Web-Application	A policy support system to aid in conservation prioritization by considering biodiversity, ESs, existing human impacts, and potential future threats.	Climate change; Biodiversity; Social values	11 All (Except for 1.2,4,5)	(Mulligan M, 2017)
6	EcoActuary	Web-Application	Application to visualize the impact of NBS mitigating Flood catastrophe	water management	11	(Mulligan et al., 2023)
7	Ecoserv-GIS	GIS-based	Maps ecosystem services and produces detailed maps that depict the human demand or desire for ecosystem services	Air quality	15	(Winn et al., 2018)
8	Free-Station & Smart	IOT to Web-Application	A sensor based IoT tool to capture environmental data in a near real-time basis.	water management	11	(Mulligan et al., 2023)
9	InVEST (Integrated Valuation of Ecosystem Services and Tradeoffs)	New benchmark with classic desktop-application	Determines how changes in ecosystems can result in shifts in the distribution of a wide array of advantages.	Climate change; water management; Air quality; Biodiversity; Soil management; Social values	10 13 14 15	(Benra et al., 2021; Tallis et al., 2010)

(Continues)

TABLE 1 (Continued)

No	Name	Type	Description	Co-benefit outputs	SDGs	example of references
10	i-Tree Eco	Web-tools	A versatile application to employ field-collected data from individual trees, comprehensive inventories, or randomly designated plots.	Climate change; water management; Air quality; Biodiversity	6 13 14 15	(Hill et al., 2021; Lin et al., 2021; Nowak et al., 2021)
11	LUCI (Land Utilisation and Capability Indicator)	GIS-based	An evolving ES modelling tool demonstrating land-use effects on diverse ESs.	Climate change; Soil management; water management; Biodiversity	6 13 15	(The LUCI team, 2019)
12	SoIVES (Social Values for Ecosystem Services)	GIS-based	A platform to foster conversations among various stakeholders concerning the trade-offs linked to ecosystem services.	Social values	11 13 17	(Sherrouse et al., 2014)

TABLE 2 Platforms that quantify public health and well-being.

Platforms	Method	Outputs
AtlasPlus	Disease data, stratified by sex, race/ethnicity, age-group, or country of birth, can be interpolated to enumerate Social Determinants of Health (SDOH).	Univariate and bivariate analysis of infectious diseases along with location specific social determinants.
BenMap	Scenario modelling of multi-pollutant concentrations is modelled using health impact functions (deaths and illness)	Economic Benefits of Improved Air Quality on health.
AccessMod	Utilizes multi-factorial analysis through dynamic linked web libraries, and Geo-spatial analyst tool-kits to compute the accessibility between demand and supply	Physical Accessibility of healthcare facilities and mode of transport.

TABLE 3 Platforms that quantify climate change parameters (carbon sequestration, carbon storage).

Platforms	Method	Outputs
ARIES	Carbon storage is quantified by linking land cover/use, forest cover, continental factors, and fire history with reference tables.	Total carbon stored in aboveground/ belowground vegetation, and the top 200 cm of soil
InVEST	Carbon storage is estimated by land cover/ use reference table. If future scenario is available, sequestration is estimated using linear interpolation.	Total carbon stored and sequestered in soil, vegetation above and below ground, and dead biomass
i-Tree Eco	Quantifying carbon storage and sequestration rates by employing allometric equations based on characteristics of tree structure.	Total carbon stored in biomass and the initial 30–100 cm of soil, carbon sequestration, net emissions
Co\$tingNature	Assesses carbon storage by economic valuation linked to the carbon sequestration capacity of ecosystems.	Carbon Storage (from living plant biomass and soil)

contributing to the exploration of Big Data Analysis and 'Infodemiology' in public health research (Kim Elmore, 2017).

BenMap and AccessMod has capabilities to generate baseline models and scenario analysis, however AtlasPlus provides univariate and bi-variate analysis by comparing diseases

TABLE 4 Platforms that quantify water management and quality benefits.

Platforms	Method	Outputs
FreeStation & Smart	(i) Use open-source hardware, and 3-D printing technology to create data loggers and sensors; (ii) Data Collection and Integration via SD cards or streaming and analyse it on the platform, that offers raw data access, graphical summaries, and integration with tools like WaterWorld and Co \$tingNature for decision support.	water quality parameters (pH), river hydrology parameters and barometric pressure
EcoActuary	Catastrophe modelling tool to simulate water-related spatial events and perform economic valuations of floods using detailed global spatial datasets and integrate remote sensing data and assessing risk probability and financial implications.	Spatial vulnerability maps for flood risks, Insurance oriented asset economic risks summary
LUCI	Integrates diverse spatial datasets within a GIS framework to simulate water flow, nutrient accumulation, and habitat connectivity across the landscape.	water quality
InVEST	Spatial mapping and risk assuagements for water quality, coastal water ecosystems, urban waters, seasonal water yield and water security. It uses linear regression for evaluations.	Actual and potential evapotranspiration, water yield, total extraction.
ARIES	Modeling ecosystem services is a part here, that involves integrating diverse ecosystem models into a flexible platform using Bayesian probabilistic techniques to propagate uncertainty.	water quality simple supply and demand estimates

and socio-demographics using GIS and Information and Communications Technology (ICT).

The use of these platforms can significantly contribute to Public Health Policy. Although, BenMap program was developed by United States EPA, it is also widely used across the world to improve

TABLE 5 Platforms that quantify air quality and temperature cooling.

Platforms	Method	Outputs
i-Tree Eco	Estimated air pollution removed by trees, grasses, and shrubs. The model requires vegetation coverage data, as well as weather and pollutant data.	Alteration in pollutant levels
BenMap	provides "roll-back" features, enabling the simulation of air pollutant epidemiology scenarios.	Impacts of PM2.5 and Ozone on diseases and premature deaths
Ecoserv-GIS	The GIS maps are used to generate the ecosystem needs and necessity.	The relative capability and need for reducing air pollution
InVEST	The InVEST urban cooling model calculates the stream temperature, and an index-based assessment of heat mitigation	Temperature Cooling

public health quality. For instance, the Georgia Environmental Protection Department (Cohan et al., 2007) uses BenMap to assess health benefits of reducing population exposure to multi-pollutant concentrations of PM 2.5 and Ozone. AccessMod is being used by health ministries of low and middle-income countries for evidence-informed policy-making and localized health service-delivery interventions (WHO, UNFPA, UNICEF and Mailman School of Public Health Averting Maternal Death and Disability, 2009). The extensive use of AccessMod by CDC demonstrates the advantage of using public health surveillance systems to evolve public health policy initiatives and programs.

3.2 | Climate change

Carbon storage plays a crucial role in the climate change. However, efficiently assessing changes resulting from NBSs remains a challenge. In this context, five widely used platforms listed in Table 3 are employed for this purpose. These platforms can contribute to SDG 13, specially 13.3: "Build knowledge and capacity to meet climate change." Generally, the carbon storage of an ecosystem is determined by calculating the average carbon density across four carbon pools (soil, aboveground vegetation, belowground vegetation, soil, and dead biomass) of each and use/land cover type by their respective areas (Tallis et al., 2011). ARIES utilizes Bayesian network models to incorporate various factors influencing carbon sequestration, including vegetation, soils, and climate (Villa et al., 2009). i-Tree Eco is a software specifically designed to assess the environmental impacts of trees in an urban area, providing valuable insights into their societal value (Hill et al., 2022). The latest version, version 6, is a versatile platform that can utilize field data from individual trees, comprehensive surveys, or randomly placed sampling sites across a study area (Nowak

TABLE 6 Platforms that quantify Biodiversity benefits.

Platforms	Method	Outputs
i-Tree Eco	Uses the Wildlife Habitat Tool to forecast the suitability of habitats for nine bird species, considering factors like land use, building cover, and vegetation characteristics.	Habitat suitability (0–1)
InVEST	Estimates biodiversity variables via these three models: Habitat quality, Habitat risk assessment, and GLOBIO.	The degradation, quality, and rarity of habitat relative to specific ecosystems Habitat ecosystem-specific risk The average species abundance
Co\$tingNature	C-value (contribution of a specific area to the global species inventory (Barthlott, 2001) of a pixel for a given species is calculated as 1/G (G: the number of pixels in which the species occurs). Endemism richness of a site is thus the sum of C-values for all the species for which data is available.	Relative richness and endemism scores (0 to 1) for red-listed reptiles, birds, mammals, and amphibians.
LUCI	By analysing established species habitats, patch size prerequisites, and dispersal capabilities via BEETLE model.	Habitat connectivity classification

TABLE 7 Platforms that quantify Soil management (erosion).

Platforms	Method	Outputs
ARIES	Estimates soil erosion using the RUSLE in combination with land cover data. It also has the flexibility to include probabilistic methods if needed.	Soil loss, soil loss avoided by vegetation
LUCI	Estimates soil erosion using RUSLE and Identifies areas with high risk of gully and rill erosion or depositing sediments into nearby water features using the Topographic Wetness Index (Beven and Kirkby, 1979)	Soil loss, erosion risk, Erosion vulnerability risk
InVEST	Estimates soil erosion using RUSLE and the proportion of sediment reaching streams (following Borselli, et al, 2008)	Soil loss, sediment exported and retention

TABLE 8 Platforms that quantify social values, tourism, aesthetic appeal, and recreation.

Platforms	Method	Outputs
InVEST	Linear regression models to estimate the primary factors (natural features, infrastructure, land uses) that influence visitation rates.	Visitation rate; Regression coefficients
Co\$ting Nature	Nature-based tourism services assessed in terms of the relative density of regional photographs.	A collection of summary maps presented on a relative scale from 0 to 1
SolVES	Produces statistical models showing the correlation between respondents' locations, relative social value allocations, and landscape features that may explain the geographical distribution and varying degrees of these social values.	A raster dataset, representing a "value index ranking" (0-10), quantifying the relative value of each social value category
ARIES	Recreation: by a travel distance, with its value diminishing in a Gaussian manner as one moves away from the source. Aesthetic value: the conceptual model incorporating two separate Bayesian networks for the independent calculation of aesthetic amenities and visual blight.	Site quality for various activities including birding, hunting, hiking, canoeing, and wildlife viewing; The spatial scope and population density of recreational area; the aesthetic appeal of the landscape in comparison to other areas

et al., 2014). To use this platform, input data such as tree species, trunk diameter at breast height (DBH), height, canopy extend, canopy health and fullness, light exposure to the crown, distance and direction to the nearest building, life expectancy, tree typology, and brown-field site identification is required (Hill et al., 2022).

The widely utilized InVEST platform assesses changes in carbon stocks due to Land Use/Land Cover (LULC) activities, requiring carbon density data (obtained from literature sources) (Zhao et al., 2019). By analyzing multi-temporal land-use maps, it allows us to estimate changes in carbon storage across the area and analyze how LULC affect carbon storage (Tallis et al., 2011). Utilizing the carbon density approach, InVEST employs LULC type maps in conjunction with data on soil, carbon stock in aboveground/ belowground

vegetation, soil, and dead biomass to evaluate the impact of LULC changes on carbon sequestration over time (Tallis et al., 2011).

Co\$tingNature is an accessible web platform that employs an integration of resource data and satellite LiDAR, along with optical and radar imagery. It assesses carbon storage by quantifying the monetary value linked to the carbon sequestration capacity of ecosystems (Delpy et al., 2021). The choice of model depends on the specific objectives of the assessment or landscape under consideration. ARIES is suitable for broader regional assessments, while iTree Eco and Co\$tingNature cater to more localized and land-use-specific inquiries. Co\$tingNature's application at smaller urban site scales is hindered by limited output reliability and its coarse resolution (Chan et al., 2021). It leverages existing datasets to provide mean values for training finer-grained models, enabling the estimation of changes in carbon sequestration via different scenarios or higher resolution modeling (Villa et al., 2009). However, its dependency on available data can pose challenges in regions where data is scarce or incomplete. Moreover, variations in land use and vegetation types may impact its accuracy. i-Tree Eco is particularly effective for assessing urban forests but can also be applied to larger areas through randomly plot-based sampling (Nowak et al., 2014). Nonetheless, to use this platform, input data must be collected by a trained team (Hill et al., 2022), and the overall quality of the outputs heavily depends on the precision of the user-collected data (Nowak et al., 2014). The sample inventory figures are estimated by extrapolation from the sample plots (Hill et al., 2022).

Among the listed platforms, i-Tree Eco stands out for its ability to calculate the sum of monetary values attributed to carbon sequestration as annual benefits (Hill et al., 2022). It employs a central computing engine that relies on scientific equations to estimate the environmental and economic advantages (Lin et al., 2021). On the other hand, the InVEST holds the distinction of being the most widely used platforms, with numerous researchers employing it for empirical studies at various scales (Delphin et al., 2013; Polasky et al., 2011). Additionally, LUCI, a dynamic model, focuses on the impact of land-use changes on carbon sequestration. It simulates various land-use scenarios and estimates carbon storage changes due to activities such as deforestation, afforestation, and urbanization. However, its current usage (its functions at carbon storage, emission) is limited to specific countries, such as UK and New Zealand (The LUCI team, 2019). However, it is worth noting that LUCI is continuously evolving and can potentially be enhanced or adapted for use in other countries as well.

The use of these platforms in policy-making highlights the importance of quantifying the benefits of carbon storage/sequestered to inform sustainable development and climate mitigation strategies. For example, the GLA has used i-Tree Eco to quantify the carbon storage benefits of London's urban forest. This data supports policies aimed at increasing urban greening and managing the city's tree population to enhance environmental benefits (Greater London Authority, GLA, 2015). Co\$tingNature was used identify critical areas for conservation and reforestation, guiding policy decisions in Ecuador (Mulligan, 2017). ARIES was applied to model ecosystem services,

including carbon storage, to support the EU Biodiversity Strategy (Schägner et al., 2013). InVEST was used to assess the carbon storage potential of different land use scenarios in Scotland's National Planning Framework (Bagstad et al., 2013).

3.3 | Water management and quality

From the listed platforms in the Table 4, can be effectively used to measure the potential contribution of NBS measures to SDG 6, "Clean Water and Sanitation" and SDG 15.1 "Conserve and restore terrestrial and freshwater ecosystems." The FreeStation is an initiative for software with different low-cost sensors deployed along with the weather stations, such as LiDAR for river discharge monitoring (Burke et al., 2023). This self-built hardware platform has been combined with the Smart:River and Smart:Soil systems for on-site monitoring and online analysis with the near real-time visualization (Mulligan et al., 2023). This platform provides educational material to deploy the sensors and using the FreeStation platform to collect and monitor the data. This can be combined with any existing standard sensor data or field data to further the studies and provide NBSs to the challenges such as floods, river discharge, forest floods and many other water management factors.

The EcoActuary platform is a suite of tools designed for assessing different types of natural flood management (NFM) across a wide range of scales (Mulligan et al., 2023). The main idea for the design is to focus on locations where minimal or no pre-existing data is accessible. The toolkit has three components to support risk analysis, NFM planning and NFM performance monitoring for installed interventions (Mulligan et al., 2023). The toolkit uses pre-existing global datasets related to global climate change, making it easier for the user to build their own models using the available datasets. For the weather data, rainfall intensities and volumes with the events can be visualized to create the flood model (Scrieciuc et al., 2023).

LUCI platform illustrates the effects of land use on diverse ecosystem services. Using spatially explicit methods, the platform enables exploration of a landscape's capacity to deliver a range of ecosystem services, including trade-offs, soil erosion, habitat connectivity, carbon storage, and flood mitigation (Jackson et al., 2013), further water quality factors such as nitrogen and phosphorus. It is used to identify the nutrient flux from land to water and in watersheds to quantify the data and provide solutions to reduce the loss of nutrients for New Zealand landscape (Trodahl et al., 2017). LUCI is designed to assessing the farm activities effect on water quality and to develop algorithms that consider variables affecting nutrient loss such as, rainfall, topography, soil type, and fertilizer use (Trodahl et al., 2017). Another platform, ARIES, are developed for water management, and it uses a variety of spatial data to map water supply and regulation services on the landscape. The modules use a simple SCS curve number or Budyko curve method to study the precipitation and evapotranspiration parameters, whereas the infiltration data is used for simple supply and demand estimates (Bagstad et al., 2011). The model mainly operates at an annual scale due to limitations in the spatial availability

of data. Regarding water management, InVEST shows three primary models, they are: Seasonal Water Yield Model (SWYM), Annual Water Yield (AWY) and Urban Stormwater Retention Model (USRM) (Benra et al., 2021; Tallis et al., 2011). Among them SWYM is based on the curve number method with inputs land cover and monthly average rainfall to estimate the monthly quick flow, whereas the outputs are spatial indices that quantify relative contribution of land to the underground, surface, and subsurface water (Benra et al., 2021). Another module in the InVEST framework known as urban flood mitigation is designed to accommodate the hydrological aspects of urban areas for better implementation in policy research. The module uses a widely accepted empirical method with very less data requirements, known as soil conservation service-curve number (SCS-CN) approach to quantify the run-off and rainfall implications of water balance equation (Kadaverugu et al., 2021). Though the module helps the policy makers in flood mitigation, only a limited few have addressed the assessment factor for damage (Kadaverugu et al., 2021).

InVEST and ARIES are specifically designed for ecosystem services and are easily accessible to non-experts and can facilitate the decision-making process, when compared with traditional hydrologic models like Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) (Jujnovsky et al., 2017). ARIES demands less data and expertise compared to other platforms, being useful for policy makers and non-technical users with limited access to data. However, the limitation in ARIES is lack of transparency due to its complex code. In contrast, while InVEST has an advantage with its relatively transparent code, making it easy to explain and modify as necessary. On the other hand, InVEST can work with ability to integrate with existing hydrological models, such as SWAT with strong technical features, into a unified platform if needed. Freestation proves to be a valuable platform for extracting data from various sources, including internet of things (IoT) sensors, partial stations, or full standard stations. It can analysis the collected data from multiple stations (Mulligan et al., 2023). Unlike Freestation, all platforms discussed in this section primarily serve as modeling tools for water management and are not designed for real-time data stream processing or uncertainty analysis for further data analysis using the continuous stream of data. However, the limitation with the Freestation is that it can be more useful when IoT or station data is available.

These platforms provide insights for developing effective strategies to manage water resources, mitigate flood risks, and enhance water quality, contributing to more sustainable and resilient water management practices. For example, FreeStation, equipped with low-cost sensors and LiDAR was applied by Thames Water in real-time monitoring of water quality parameters and managing the water distribution system efficiently (Thames Water, 2020). EcoActuary was utilized by Scottish EPA to inform policies to reduce flood risks (Scottish Environmental Protection Agency, SEPA, 2018). InVEST has been used in the Netherlands Delta Programme to evaluate the impacts of different land and water management strategies on water quality and flood risk. This supports the development of adaptive water management policies to protect against sea level rise and extreme weather events (Delta Programme Commissioner, DPC, 2020).

3.4 | Air quality and temperature cooling

There are some platforms to valuate air quality and temperature cooling (Table 5). The change in concentration of air pollutants by dry deposition on vegetation (Using tree, shrub, and grass cover data) can be estimated by i-Tree Eco platform. Air pollution reduction is estimated by modeling the exchange of gases and the interception of particulate matter by trees, grass, and shrubs for various pollutants, including particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), sulfur dioxide, nitrogen dioxide, carbon monoxide, and ozone (Vigerstol & Aukema, 2011).

BenMap, provides “roll-back” features, enabling the simulation of air pollutant epidemiology scenarios. Specifically, it assesses the impacts of PM_{2.5} and Ozone on diseases and premature deaths. However, BenMap currently lacks the capability to estimate air pollutant epidemiology for concentrations like Methane, Nitrogen Oxides, Sulfur Oxides, or Bituminous Coal. Nevertheless, the platform allows users to evaluate various emission control scenarios and predict future air quality trends for a specific location. This platform offers the flexibility for users to upload custom datasets for any location worldwide (BenMAP-CE, 2023).

Moreover, the two platforms including Invest and Ecoserv-GIS are capable to evaluate the cooling effect of urban nature. In the case of Invest, the cooling effect is simulated based on multiple factors, including albedo, air temperature, shade, evapotranspiration, and the enhanced cooling potential of larger urban green areas (Veerkamp et al., 2023). On the other hand, Ecoserv-GIS measures the relative potential and need for reducing air pollution. The natural environment's capacity for air purification is assessed by assigning air purification scores to generalized habitat types, considering their pollutant-trapping capabilities. Subsequently, regions around vegetation that have the potential to reduce air pollution are identified. For societal demand of air purification, the assessment is based on population density calculations within urban areas. In contrast, regulatory demand is determined by estimating air pollution levels related to traffic. These estimates rely on a reverse distance approach from roads, categorized by road type, with the assumption that higher category roads have increased traffic. It is presumed in this platform that a variety of mapping resources such as Open Space Survey, habitat mapping, Landscape Character, or Green Infrastructure mapping are readily available (Winn et al., 2018). InVEST attributes cooling mainly to tree shading, while considering the cooling impact of other vegetation types and water bodies through estimation of evapotranspiration and surface albedo based on LULC classes areas (Veerkamp et al., 2023).

i-Tree Eco offers an economic valuation feature, which is estimated in two ways (Hirabayashi, 2018): 1. quantifying the societal cost of air pollution, which is typically not reflected in the market prices of the goods or services responsible for the air pollution, and 2. evaluating the number of incidents prevented and the overall monetary value associated with various health factors linked to four pollutants: SO₂, NO₂, O₃, and PM_{2.5}.

Estimating the cost of air pollution to society and estimating the number of incidents avoided and the total dollar value of various

health factors related to four pollutants (NO₂, SO₂, O₃, and PM_{2.5}), can be derived from BenMAP model (Lin et al., 2021). These valuations are originally based on data from the US but can be replaced with regionally appropriate statistics for international case studies (Lin et al., 2021; Nowak et al., 2014).

These tools provide valuable insights into the potential of green infrastructure to mitigate air pollution and urban heat islands. i-Tree Eco offers economic valuation of air pollution reductions through vegetation, guiding cost-effective urban greening decisions. BenMAP has been extensively used by the U.S. EPA to estimate the health and economic benefits of air quality regulations. It has been instrumental in assessing the impact of the Clean Air Act, providing data that supports the formulation and revision of national air quality standards (U.S. Environmental Protection Agency (U.S. EPA, 2019). InVEST and Ecoserv-GIS assess cooling effects of NBSs, assisting in resilient urban design against climate risks.

3.5 | Biodiversity

Biodiversity encompasses the full spectrum of life, encompassing genetic, species, and functional trait variations (Yang et al., 2021). It stands as a fundamental outcome and a primary co-benefit NBSs. Various approaches have been introduced to measure biodiversity, ranging from species count to the utilization of indices like Shannon's diversity index and the emergy method (Yang et al., 2021). These methods often rely on ecological models (Gotelli & Colwell, 2001) and distribution models (Araújo et al., 2019). However, grappling with data constraints and the inherent intricacies of biological systems has been a challenge for these models (Araújo et al., 2019). Both models strive to establish links between resulting factors (like species richness, habitat suitability, and changes in species composition) and environmental elements, often utilizing data-centric statistical methods (Elith & Leathwick, 2009; Ferrier et al., 2007). These methods also depend on comparable data that are usually essential for implementing the GLOBIO model. GLOBIO4, an open-source framework utilizing Python and geospatial libraries, executes diverse biodiversity pressure-response modules. The GLOBIO-Species extension assesses human impacts on vertebrate species' distribution and population size, yielding multi-species indicators like the Red List Index (RLI) and the Living Planet Index (LPI). RLI gauges extinction risk changes, while LPI tracks population abundance shifts across species. These indicators are crucial for monitoring global biodiversity targets (Barbarossa et al., 2020).

Some variables related to biodiversity are quantified by the models listed in the Table 6. i-Tree Eco, for instance, presently forecasts habitat suitability for only nine bird species. This prediction is based on LULC and vegetation attributes, facilitated by the WILDLIFE HABITAT tool. Each bird habitat model within this tool generates a habitat suitability index ranging from 0 to 1. However, the habitat assessment approach has certain limitations, as discussed in detail by (Lerman et al., 2014). Notably, further research is required to explore how the valuation of multitude of wildlife species can be simulated (Lin et al., 2021). The LUCI platform's habitat connectivity tool is

utilizable to identify suitable zones for expanding and safeguarding habitats. This platform employs a cost-distance methodology to assess habitat connectivity. LUCI streamlines this process and adopts Forest Research's parameters for chosen habitats (Watts et al., 2007, 2010). InVEST encompasses three distinct methods for quantifying different aspects: mean species abundance (MSA) through the InVEST GLOBIO Model, identifying existing ecosystem risks via Habitat Risk Assessment, and evaluating habitat quality, rarity, and degradation using the Habitat Quality Model. These approaches depend on land use changes and nearby threats (Sharp et al., 2018). It is important to note that using individual species as a proxy for biodiversity might not always be appropriate. Validating this assumption is essential, especially when considering species that share close taxonomic and ecological characteristics (Loman et al., 2021). Finally, Co\$tingNature platform, measures Conservation priority and produce relative richness and endemism scores results. Secondary data is frequently derived from raw biodiversity data or remote sensing methods. For instance, Global Forest Watch platform provides up-to-date data, technology, and tools for enhanced forest protection (Beker et al., 2019). Various models and platforms, like MARXAN (Serra-Sogas et al., 2013), and REMAP (Murray et al., 2018), monitor land cover and biodiversity, supplying valuable insights for decision-making.

The above-mentioned platforms provide robust methodologies to monitor biodiversity across different spatial scales and ecosystems. Those contribute to assessing the effectiveness of NBSs on SDG 15.5 "Protect biodiversity and natural habitats." There are some examples demonstrate how these platforms can translate scientific data into actionable policies that promote biodiversity conservation. Belfast city implemented i-Tree Eco studies to understand the structure and benefits of the urban forests, making effective resource management decisions, developing policy, and setting priorities for a town's trees (Hill et al., 2022). The results of a study using InVEST were useful for plant biodiversity conservation policy-making and human activity management for the disaster-impacted mountainous areas in China (Gong et al., 2019). And CostingNature has been used for Biodiversity strategy and action for the UK (King's College London, 2023).

3.6 | Soil management

Assessing soil characteristics and land boundaries is vital for land suitability evaluation, supporting sustainable land management and reducing land use impacts (D'Antonio et al., 2024). Soil management is a co-benefit of some NBSs which can be monitored with soil erosion. Soil erosion control is modeled by four platforms listed in the Table 7. Contribution to SDG 15 "Life on Land" can be also assessed by them. Among these platforms, InVEST has a potential to offer economic valuation. Most of soil erosion quantification models derive from the Revised Universal Soil Loss Equation (RUSLE) and its modified versions. The RUSLE, specifically, predicts annual soil erosion resulting from sheet and rill erosion. It considers Various elements, including rainfall erosivity, topography, soil erodibility, erosion control practices,

and land use management, to estimate soil erosion in a specific area (Igwe et al., 2017). While LUCC and InVEST emphasize the utilization of established biophysical relationships (where applicable) for modeling physical processes, ARIES goes beyond standard modeling techniques through model wrapping by also incorporating probabilistic methods, such as Bayesian networks, when there is a lack of sufficient local data to apply in biophysical equations. On the other hand, employing the ARIES internal rule base for model selection allows for the integration of RUSLE, complemented with suitable Bayesian erosion models, in cases of steeper slopes or where RUSLE alone is insufficient (Bagstad et al., 2011). InVEST and LUCI incorporate spatial models designed to ease the movement of materials within watersheds and their transport into stream networks or water bodies. This integration enables a more intricate modeling approach, considering the arrangement and makeup of various land cover types throughout the study area. However, to achieve dependable results, this approach often necessitates highly detailed terrain data and appropriate calibration (López-Vicente & Álvarez, 2018). The resolution of topographic data can significantly influence the outcomes of soil loss models. However, determining the optimal resolution requires striking a balance between availability of data, processing times, and the intended application of model outputs (Schoorl et al., 2000). Due to the limitations of The RUSLE in capturing certain vital erosion mechanisms, some alternative approaches to erosion quantification have been proposed (Daly et al., 2015). Additionally, the Soil and Water Assessment Tool (SWAT) is a conventional hydrological tool that relies on the empirical Modified Universal Soil Loss Equation (MUSLE). However, to assess ecosystem services, post-processing is necessary for using SWAT (Li et al., 2022).

The integration of LUCI, ARIES, and InVEST into policy-making has led to more informed and effective environmental policies. The Welsh Government used LUCI to inform its sustainable land management policies by identifying high-risk erosion areas (Welsh Government 2018). The UNDP utilized ARIES to value ecosystem services, including soil retention, to support national policies in countries like Colombia and Kenya. Policies influenced by ARIES include Payment for Ecosystem Services and Integrated Water Resource Management (United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), 2019). In the United States, InVEST has been used extensively by the Natural Capital Project to inform a variety of policies at the state and federal levels. Some examples include California's Sustainable Groundwater Management Act (California Department of Water Resources, 2014) and Puget Sound Partnership's Recovery Plan (2016).

3.7 | Socioeconomic values

The social values of NBS are the perceived non-market values that the public attributes to NBS, especially cultural services such as recreation and esthetic appeal. These values can differ for different stakeholder groups, and these digital tools help monitor these attitudes and preferences (Mulligan (2017); Sherrouse et al., 2020). The platforms listed in the Table 8 value social values, esthetic appeal, and

recreation. They can contribute to SDG 12 a “develop and implement tools to monitor sustainable tourism.” Among those, SolVES stands out for its distinctive approach, which is centered on statistically correlating social values with spatially explicit environmental layers. It links any social values, such as cultural, historic esthetics and spiritual values as well as future generation and potential recreation activities. In achieving this, pertinent stakeholders and local communities are engaged to extract social value through public attitudes (Sherrouse et al., 2020). The other platform, Co\$tingNature contains global dataset that by using them together with default parameters, evaluating ecosystem services in the worldwide terrestrial environment is achievable without any additional data input requirements (Mulligan (2017)).

InVEST employs a proxy measure for visitation, leveraging the correlation derived from geotagged photographs shared on the Flickr website, and the actual number of individuals visiting a particular location. Certain recreational activities may also be well-suited for photography. ARIES, in other hand, covers multiple case study areas focusing on esthetic value and recreational services (Hung & Hsu, 2022).

The techniques utilized by both InVEST and SolVES to value recreation are adaptable and can be applied across various scales. However, there exist constraints in the outcomes generated and in how they are understood. Neither platform directly calculates the quantity of visits nor gauges the well-being experienced by individuals due to their access to the recreational site. Co\$ting Nature calculates potential recreational services by connecting aspects of the accessibility of a natural landscape to the population (Mulligan et al., 2020). This assessment is then merged with a geotagged photograph database, like the approach employed by InVEST. Besides, it can calculate the contributions of nature to the SDGs (Mulligan (2017)).

There are some examples demonstrate how these platforms can provide crucial data to influence policy decisions. For example, In Belize, the results from InVEST helped policymakers establish zones for tourism, fishing, and conservation that maximize benefits while minimizing conflicts (Garrido & Sanchez, 2020). SolVES was used to assess the social values associated with different land use scenarios in Teton County, forming local policies to align land use decisions with community values and preferences for conservation and recreation (Brown et al., 2015). And Co\$tingNature quantified the benefits of tourism, recreation, and coastal protection in Kenya, supporting sustainable coastal management policies and investment decisions by highlighting the economic benefits of preserving these ecosystems (O'Neill et al., 2014).

3.8 | Stakeholder engagement platforms

There are other open-access platforms that help communities to be resilient through monitoring the consequences of different NBS strategies. Financial innovation which plays a pivotal role in stimulating economic activities, can be applied based on these platforms (Chishti et al., 2021). These platforms facilitate societal transitions. They provide a place for involving communities and other stakeholders to share and use data. They can be effectively used by different stakeholders, including policymakers, corporations, environmental

organizations, citizens, and more. These platforms mostly monitor land cover/ land use variation, reforestation, carbon emission and recourse provisions. These platforms, along with brief descriptions, are listed in Table S3. As an example, the Cool Farm Tool, endorsed by prominent academics and NGOs dedicated to agricultural sustainability, empowers farmers in mitigating carbon emissions and fostering biodiversity. Reducing tillage and adding cover crops can reduce and even sequester emissions while building soil health. But each farm and field respond differently. The tool accommodates variations in response within different farms and fields, allowing farmers to tailor their management practices (Hillier et al., 2011). Some other platforms such as Nature4Cities, provide examples of implemented NBS projects together with their detailed co-benefits and a tool to determine if these projects are replicable in a specific area. The Think Nature Platform is a versatile, multi-stakeholder communication platform that facilitates the comprehension and promotion of Nature-Based Solutions. It fosters continuous dialog and interaction surrounding NBS, promoting collaboration at local, regional, national, and EU levels, which enables smooth societal transitions. Furthermore, it strives to establish synergies with other NBS projects (Somarakis et al., 2019).

3.9 | Gaps and potential opportunities for future development

So far, there are no open-access platforms to quantify the co-benefits of environmental justice within NBS, a significant gap since environmental justice ensures equitable access to environmental benefits and addresses disparities. Existing platforms only partially address social values and fail to cover community cohesion, cultural heritage, and recreational benefits comprehensively. Their effectiveness is limited by data availability. Additionally, most platforms rely on historical datasets for modeling and analysis, not continuous sensor data, due to the complexity and calibration required.

Despite their robustness, these platforms are siloed, designed for specific purposes and disciplines, limiting their ability to promote the transdisciplinary approaches needed for successful NBS implementation. This specialized focus can lead to uncoordinated environmental management efforts, complicating the resolution of complex sustainability issues. For instance, while platforms like Nature4Cities and ThinkNature (Table S3) encourage collaboration and multi-stakeholder engagement, they lack the comprehensive modeling capabilities of platforms like InVEST or ARIES. This siloed nature of current platforms underscores the need for more integrative platforms that can bridge disciplinary gaps and support cohesive policy development.

Furthermore, digital platforms for evaluating NBS struggle with the site-specific details, which are crucial for effective scaling and maximizing co-benefits. platforms like InVEST and the Cool Farm Tool offer robust models for ecosystem services and agricultural practices, but their effectiveness heavily depends on the quality and resolution of local data, which can vary significantly, thereby impacting the accuracy and relevance of their outputs. Moreover, platforms like ARIES and LUCI, are often constrained by their specific parameters and

objectives, making them less flexible in accommodating broader environmental and social factors. Their adaptation requires significant technical expertise, thus complicating implementation. Therefore, future development should focus on modular, user-friendly tools that incorporate new data and parameters easily, supporting iterative, real-world applications and fostering collaborative frameworks for effective NBS scaling and maximizing co-benefits.

It is worth mentioning that ICT plays a crucial role in creating a digital infrastructure for collecting and managing data related to NBS initiatives, such as databases, cloud-based storage, and web-based platforms for easy access and information sharing. GIS enables spatial analysis and visualization of NBS data, helping stakeholders identify hotspots, track changes, and make informed decisions. Remote sensing, involving data collection from satellites and airborne sensors, provides insights into the environmental impact of NBS. And IoT technology integrates various sensors and devices to collect real-time data and continuously monitor NBS solutions. Combination of these technologies are not only valuable tools for collecting, analyzing, and visualizing the data, but also are leading to more enhanced evidence-based decision-making for stakeholders that are involved in the implementation and evaluation of NBS solutions.

4 | CONCLUSION

NBS usually offer a range of benefits, including but not limited to improved air quality, carbon storage, reduced urban heat island effect, increased biodiversity, enhanced water management, and community well-being. The digital platforms reviewed in this paper have emerged to transform implementations in NBS. Some of these platforms, like InVEST, ARIES, and i-Tree-Eco offer multiple tools and models to quantify specific benefits of NBS, they are not able to capture all the co-benefits provided by implementing NBS. The platforms predominantly prioritize aspects such as carbon storage, air quality, and water and soil management—benefits directly aligned with SDGs 6, 11, 13, and 15. The platforms predominantly prioritize aspects such as carbon storage, air quality, water and soil management—benefits directly aligned with SDGs 6, 11, 13, and 15. To comprehensively assess the multiple benefits of NBS, it may require using a combination of tools and approaches specific to each benefit or employing integrated assessment frameworks.

Additionally, most of these platforms rely on historical datasets for their modeling and analysis. They use these datasets to simulate scenarios and generate geospatial models that help assess the potential impacts of NBS. Due to the complexity and calibration of these models, they are typically designed to work with historical data rather than continuous sensor data. On the other hand, most of the platforms apply GIS (e.g., Ecoserv-GIS and LUCI) some of them use Remote Sensing (e.g., Co\$tingNature), ICT (e.g., AtlasPlus), and IOT (e.g., Free-Station & Smart) separately. Combination of these technologies are not only valuable tools for collecting, analyzing, and visualizing the data, but also are leading to more enhanced evidence-based decision-making for stakeholders that are involved in the implementation and evaluation of NBS solutions.

By highlighting the strengths and limitations of existing platforms, this paper emphasizes the importance of developing transdisciplinary methodologies that align with the UNEA definition of NBS, promoting synergies across environmental, social, and economic dimensions to achieve SDGs.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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REFERENCES

- Aghimien, D., Aliu, J., Chan, D. W. M., Aigbavboa, C., & Awuzie, B. (2024). Making a case for nature-based solutions for a sustainable built environment in Africa. *Sustainable Development*, 32(5), 4686–4706. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.2935>
- Alvarado, O., Alfonso, O., Medrano, A., Bierkens, M., Prusina, I., & Contact, A. (2019). Measuring the benefits of urban nature-based solutions through quantitative assessment tools MSc water science and management [Unpublished MSc dissertation]. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34098.84163>
- Araújo, M. B., Anderson, R. P., Barbosa, A. M., Beale, C. M., Dormann, C. F., Early, R., Garcia, R. A., Guisan, A., Maiorano, L., Naimi, B., O'Hara, R. B., Zimmermann, N. E., & Rahbek, C. (2019). Standards for distribution models in biodiversity assessments. *Science Advances*, 5(1), 4858–4874. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.aat4858>
- Bagstad, K. J., Semmens, D. J., Waage, S., & Winthrop, R. (2013). A comparative assessment of decision-support tools for ecosystem services quantification and valuation. *Ecosystem Services*, 5, 27–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2013.07.004>
- Bagstad, K. J., Villa, F., Johnson, G. W., & Voigt, B. (2011). ARIES (artificial intelligence for ecosystem services): A guide to models and data, version 1.0. *Aries Report Series*, 1, 95–108. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13398-014-0173-7>
- Balzan, M. V., Geneletti, D., Grace, M., De Santis, L., Tomaskinova, J., Reddington, H., Sapundzhieva, A., Dicks, L. V., & Collier, M. (2022). Assessing nature-based solutions uptake in a Mediterranean climate: Insights from the case-study of Malta. *Nature-Based Solutions*, 2, 100029. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.NbSj.2022.100029>
- Barbarossa, V., Schmitt, R. J. P., Huijbregts, M. A. J., Zarfl, C., King, H., & Schipper, A. M. (2020). Impacts of current and future large dams on the geographic range connectivity of freshwater fish worldwide. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 117(7), 3648–3655. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1912776117>
- Barthlott, W., Schmit-Neuerburg, V., Nieder, J., & Engwald, S. (2001). Diversity and abundance of vascular epiphytes: A comparison of secondary vegetation and primary montane rain forest in the Venezuelan Andes. *Plant Ecology*, 152, 145–156.
- Beker, T., Orlović, S., & Stojanović, D. B. (2019). Overview of free open source global forest species data for biogeographic modeling. *Topola Poplar*, 204, 59–70.
- BenMAP-CE. (2023). Environmental benefits mapping and analysis program-community edition. User's manual.
- Benra, F., Frutos, A. D., Gaglio, M., Álvarez-Garretón, C., Felipe-Lucia, M., & Bonn, A. (2021). Mapping water ecosystem services: Evaluating InVEST model predictions in data scarce regions. *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 138, 104982. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2021.104982>
- Beven, K. J., & Kirkby, M. J. (1979). A physically based, variable contributing area model of basin hydrology/Un modèle à base physique de zone d'appel variable de l'hydrologie du bassin versant. *Hydrological Sciences Journal*, 24, 43–69. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02626667909491834>
- Borselli, L., Cassi, P., & Torri, D. (2008). Prolegomena to sediment and flow connectivity in the landscape: A GIS and field numerical assessment. *Catena*, 75, 268–277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.catena.2008.07.006>
- Brown, K. R. K., Chan, R. H., & Turner, W. R. (2015). Integrating social values into land use planning: A case study of Teton County, Wyoming, USA. *Land Use Policy*, 46, 249–259.
- Burke, S., van Soesbergen, A., & Mulligan, M. (2023). Effectiveness-assessment of nature-based flood mitigation using networked, low cost DIY environmental monitoring from FreeStation. EGU General Assembly 2023, EGU23-5922. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu23-5922>
- California Department of Water Resources. (2014). California's groundwater: Working toward sustainability. <https://water.ca.gov/programs/groundwater-management/sgma-groundwater-management>
- Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, CDC. 2023, <https://www.cdc.gov/nchhstp/about/atlasplus.html>.
- Chan, K., Schillereff, D. N., Baas, A. C. W., Chadwick, M. A., Main, B., Mulligan, M., O'Shea, F. T., Pearce, R., Smith, T. E. L., van Soesbergen, A., Tebbs, E., & Thompson, J. (2021). Low-cost electronic sensors for environmental research: Pitfalls and opportunities. *Progress in Physical Geography*, 45(3), 305–338. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0309133320956566>
- Chishti, M. Z., Ahmad, M., Rehman, A., & Sinha, A. (2021). Do the shocks in technological and financial innovation influence the environmental quality? Evidence from BRICS economies. *Technology in Society*, 68, 101828. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techsoc.2021.101828>
- Cohan, D. S., Boylan, J. W., Marmur, A., & Khan, M. (2007). An integrated framework for multipollutant air quality management and its application in Georgia. *Environmental Management*, 40, 545–554. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-006-0228-4>
- Daly, E. R., Miller, R. B., & Fox, G. A. (2015). Modeling streambank erosion and failure along protected and unprotected composite streambanks. *Advances in Water Resources*, 81, 114–127. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.advwatres.2015.01.004>
- D'Antonio, P., Fiorentino, C., AbdelRahman, M. A. E., Sannino, M., Scalcione, E., Lacertosa, G., Modugno, F., Marsico, A., Donvito, A. R., Conceição, L. A., Drosos, M., & Scopa, A. (2024). Modeling climatic, terrain and soil factors using AHP in GIS for grapevines suitability assessment. *Sustainable Development*, 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.313622>
- Delphin, S., Escobedo, F. J., Abd-Elrahman, A., & Cropper, W. (2013). Mapping potential carbon and timber losses from hurricanes using a decision tree and ecosystem services driver model. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 129, 599–607. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2013.08.029>
- Delpy, F., Zari, M. P., Jackson, B., Benavidez, R., & Westend, T. (2021). Ecosystem services assessment tools for regenerative urban design in Oceania. *Sustainability*, 13(5), 1–22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13052825>
- Delta Programme Commissioner DPC. (2020). Delta Programme 2021: Continuing the work on sustainable water management. <https://english.deltacommissaris.nl/delta-programme/documents/publications/2020/09/15/delta-programme-2021>
- Dhyani, S., Kumar, A., Madhav, G., Editors, K., Sivapuram, G., Rama, V., Prabhakar, K., & Surjan, A. (2023). *Nature-based solutions for resilient ecosystems and societies*. Springer.

- El Harrak, M., & Lemaitre, F. (2023). *European roadmap to 2030 for research and innovation on nature-based solutions*. NetworkNature.
- Elith, J., & Leathwick, J. R. (2009). Species distribution models: Ecological explanation and prediction across space and time. *Annual Review of Ecology, Evolution, and Systematics*, 40(1), 677–697. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev.ecolsys.110308.120159>
- Epelde, L., Mendizabal, M., Gutiérrez, L., Artetxe, A., Garbisu, C., & Feliu, E. (2022). Quantification of the environmental effectiveness of nature-based solutions for increasing the resilience of cities under climate change. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 67, 127433. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2021.127433>
- Faivre, N., Fritz, M., Freitas, T., de Boissezon, B., & Vandewoestijne, S. (2017). Nature-based solutions in the EU: Innovating with nature to address social, economic and environmental challenges. *Environmental Research*, 159, 509–518. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2017.08.032>
- Fann, N., Fulcher, C. M., & Hubbell, B. J. (2009). The influence of location, source, and emission type in estimates of the human health benefits of reducing a ton of air pollution. *Air Quality, Atmosphere and Health*, 2(3), 169–176. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11869-009-0044-0>
- Ferrier, S., Manion, G., Elith, J., & Richardson, K. (2007). Using generalized dissimilarity modelling to analyse and predict patterns of beta diversity in regional biodiversity assessment. *Diversity and Distributions*, 13(3), 252–264. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1472-4642.2007.00341.x>
- Frantzeskaki, N., McPhearson, T., Collier, M. J., Kendal, D., Bulkeley, H., Dumitru, A., Walsh, C., Noble, K., & Van Wyk, E. (2019). Nature-based solutions for urban climate change adaptation: Linking science, policy, and practice communities for evidence-based decision-making. *Bioscience*, 69, 455–466.
- Garrido, A., & Sanchez, E. (2020). Applying InVEST for marine spatial planning in Belize: Balancing conservation and economic development. *Journal of Marine Policy*, 117, 103880. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.103880>
- Gómez Martín, E., Giordano, R., Pagano, A., van der Keur, P., & Máñez Costa, M. (2020). Using a system thinking approach to assess the contribution of nature based solutions to sustainable development goals. *Science of the Total Environment*, 738, 139693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.139693>
- Gong, J., Xie, Y., & Cao, E. (2019). Integration of InVEST-habitat quality model with landscape pattern indexes to assess mountain plant biodiversity change: A case study of Bailongjiang watershed in Gansu Province. *Journal of Geographical Sciences*, 29, 1193–1210. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11442-019-1653-7>
- Gotelli, N. J., & Colwell, R. K. (2001). Quantifying biodiversity: Procedures and pitfalls in the measurement and comparison of species richness. *Ecology Letters*, 4(4), 379–391. <https://doi.org/10.1046/j.1461-0248.2001.00230.x>
- Greater London Authority, GLA. (2015). *Valuing London's urban forest: Results of the London i-Tree Eco Project*.
- Hill, D., & Baker, S. (2021). *Oxford i-tree eco report 2021* (pp. 1–42).
- Hill, D., Ruddick, J., & Walker, J. (2022). *Valuing Belfast's urban forest*. Belfast City Council, Technical Report, i-Tree Eco Sample Survey of Belfast's Urban Forest.
- Hillier, J., Walter, C., Malin, D., Garcia-Suarez, T., Mila-i-Canals, L., & Smith, P. (2011). A farm-focused calculator for emissions from crop and livestock production. *Environmental Modelling and Software*, 26(9), 1070–1078. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2011.03.014>
- Hirabayashi, S. (2018). i-tree eco model enhancements for version 6. https://daac.ornl.gov/cgi-bin/dsvviewer.pl?ds_id=1210
- Hung, S.-H., & Hsu, J.-H. (2022). *Using the artificial intelligence for ecosystem services (ARIES) model to explore the value of socio-economic ecosystems using the Jinshan Qingshui wetland in northern Taiwan as a case study*. En SUPTM 2022: 1st Conference on Future Challenges in Sustainable Urban Planning & Territorial Management. <https://doi.org/10.31428/10317/10469>
- IPCC Core Writing Team, R.K. Pachauri and L.A. Meyer (eds.) (2014). *Climate change 2014: Synthesis report. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change IPCC*, 151 pp.
- Igwe, P. U., Onuigbo, A. A., Chinedu, O. C., Ezeaku, I. I., & Muoneke, M. M. (2017). Soil erosion: A review of models and applications. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering Research and Science*, 4(12), 138–150. <https://doi.org/10.22161/ijaers.4.12.22>
- Jackson, B., Pagella, T., Sinclair, F., Orellana, B., Henshaw, A., Reynolds, B., McIntyre, N., Wheeler, H., & Eycott, A. (2013). Polyscape: A GIS mapping framework providing efficient and spatially explicit landscape-scale valuation of multiple ecosystem services. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 112(1), 74–88. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.LANDURBPLAN.2012.12.014>
- Johnston, M. (2014). Secondary data analysis: A method of which the time has come. *Qualitative and Quantitative Methods in Libraries*, 3, 619–626.
- Jujnovsky, J., Ramos, A., Caro-Borrero, Á., Mazari-Hiriart, M., Maass, M., & Almeida-Leñero, L. (2017). Water assessment in a peri-urban watershed in Mexico City: A focus on an ecosystem services approach. *Ecosystem Services*, 24, 91–100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ECOSER.2017.02.005>
- Kabisch, N., Frantzeskaki, N., Pauleit, S., Naumann, S., Davis, M., Artmann, M., Haase, D., Knapp, S., Korn, H., Stadler, J., Zaunberger, K., & Bonn, A. (2016). Nature-based solutions to climate change mitigation and adaptation in urban areas: Perspectives on indicators, knowledge gaps, barriers, and opportunities for action. *Ecology and Society*, 21(2), 1–39. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-08373-210239>
- Kadaverugu, A., Rao, C. N., & Viswanadh, G. K. (2021). Quantification of flood mitigation services by urban green spaces using InVEST model: A case study of Hyderabad city, India. *Modeling Earth Systems and Environment*, 7(1), 589–602. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40808-020-00937-0>
- Kim Elmore, P. (2017). Maps, charts, and tables: Using the NCHSTP AtlasPlus to visualize or download CDC's HIV, viral hepatitis, STD, and TB surveillance data.
- King's College London. (2023). *Biodiversity strategy and action for the UK*. <https://www.policysupport.org/costingnature/example-applications/biodiversity-strategy-and-action-for-the-uk>
- Kumar, P., Debele, S. E., Sahani, J., Rawat, N., Marti-Cardona, B., Alfieri, S. M., Basu, B., Basu, A. S., Bowyer, P., Charizopoulos, N., Jaakko, J., Loupis, M., Menenti, M., Mickovski, S. B., Pfeiffer, J., Pilla, F., Pröll, J., Pulvirenti, B., Rutzinger, M., & Zieher, T. (2021). An overview of monitoring methods for assessing the performance of nature-based solutions against natural hazards. *Earth-Science Reviews*, 217, 103603. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2021.103603>
- Lerman, S. B., Nislow, K. H., Nowak, D. J., DeStefano, S., King, D. I., & Jones-Farrand, D. T. (2014). Using urban forest assessment tools to model bird habitat potential. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 122, 29–40. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landurbplan.2013.10.006>
- Li, D., Yuan, J., Ding, J., Wang, H., Shen, Y., & Li, G. (2022). Effects of carbon/nitrogen ratio and aeration rate on the sheep manure composting process and associated gaseous emissions. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 323, 116093. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116093>
- Lin, J., Kroll, C. N., & Nowak, D. J. (2021). An uncertainty framework for i-tree eco: A comparative study of 15 cities across the United States. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*, 60, 127062. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ufug.2021.127062>
- Loman, Z. G., Deluca, W. V., Harrison, D. J., Loftin, C. S., Schwenk, W. S., & Wood, P. B. (2021). How well do proxy species models inform conservation of surrogate species? *Landscape Ecology*, 36(10), 2863–2877. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-021-01294-8>
- López-Vicente, M., & Álvarez, S. (2018). Influence of DEM resolution on modelling hydrological connectivity in a complex agricultural catchment with woody crops. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 43(7), 1403–1415. <https://doi.org/10.1002/esp.4321>

- Malekmohammadi, S., & Mirbagheri, S. A. (2023). Scale-up single chamber of microbial fuel cell using agitator and sponge biocarriers. *Environmental Technology*, 45(15), 2935–2943. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09593330.2023.2197126>
- Mirbagheri, S. A., & Raji, M. (2017). Effects of return mixed liquor recycling ratio on A2/O process. *MCEJ*, 17(3), 227–234. <http://mcej.modares.ac.ir/article-16-8150-en.html>
- Mulligan, M. (2017). Documentation for the Co\$tingNature Model V3. Original V3 documentation.
- Mulligan, M., Burke, S., Douglas, C., & van Soesbergen, A. (2023). Methodologies to assess and map the biophysical effectiveness of nature based solutions. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-25308-9_4
- Mulligan, M., van Soesbergen, A., Hole, D. G., Brooks, T. M., Burke, S., & Hutton, J. (2020). Mapping nature's contribution to SDG 6 and implications for other SDGs at policy relevant scales. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 239, 111671. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2020.111671>
- Murray, N. J., Wilshire, J. H., & Simpson, D. (2018). *RemapUserGuide-v1.1*. Centre for Ecosystem Science. – University of New South Wales..
- Nelson, D. R., Bledsoe, B. P., Ferreira, S., & Nibbelink, N. P. (2020). Challenges to realizing the potential of nature-based solutions. *Current Opinion in Environmental Sustainability*, 45, 49–55. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2020.09.001>
- Nowak, D. J. (2021). *Understanding i-Tree*. U.S. Department of Agriculture, Forest Service, Northern Research Station. <https://doi.org/10.2737/NRS-GTR-200-2021>
- Nowak, D. J., Hirabayashi, S., Bodine, A., & Greenfield, E. (2014). Tree and forest effects on air quality and human health in the United States. *Environmental Pollution*, 193, 119–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2014.05.028>
- Ommer, J., Bucchignani, E., Leo, L. S., Kalas, M., Vranić, S., Debele, S., Kumar, P., Cloke, H. L., & Sabatino, S. D. (2022). Quantifying co-benefits and disbenefits of nature-based solutions targeting disaster risk reduction. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 75, 102966. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2022.102966>
- O'Neill, S. A. H., Dewees, M. M., & Bachelet, D. (2014). Economic valuation of ecosystem services in the Kenyan coastal region using Co\$tingNature. *Ecological Economics*, 98, 98–107.
- Poirier, O., de Castaneda, R. L. R., Bolon, I., & Ray, N. (2021). Modelling forest degradation and risk of disease outbreaks in mainland Equatorial Guinea. *Journal of Public Health and Emergency*, 5, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.21037/jphe-20-97>
- Polasky, S., Nelson, E., Pennington, D., & Johnson, K. A. (2011). The impact of land-use change on ecosystem services, biodiversity and returns to landowners: A case study in the state of Minnesota. *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 48(2), 219–242. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-010-9407-0>
- Puget Sound Partnership. (2016). Puget sound action agenda: Comprehensive plan for recovery of the puget sound.
- Qu, Z., Thrush, S., & Lewis, N. (2021). Evaluating decision-support tools for monetary valuation of ecosystem services for marine protected areas. In *Ocean and coastal management* (Vol. 215, 105951). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2021.105951>
- Ray, N., & Ebener, S. (2008). AccessMod 3.0: Computing geographic coverage and accessibility to health care services using anisotropic movement of patients. *International journal of health geographics*, 7, 63. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-072X-7-63>
- Sacks, J. D., Lloyd, J. M., Zhu, Y., Anderton, J., Jang, C. J., Hubbell, B., & Fann, N. (2018). The environmental benefits mapping and analysis program—Community edition (BenMAP-CE): A tool to estimate the health and economic benefits of reducing air pollution. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 104, 118–129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2018.02.009>
- Schägner, J. P., Brander, L., Maes, J., & Hartje, V. (2013). Mapping ecosystem services' values: Current practice and future prospects. *Ecosystem Services*, 33–46, 2212–2416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2013.02.003>
- Schoorl, J. M., Sonneveld, M. P. W., & Veldkamp, A. (2000). Three-dimensional landscape process modelling: The effect of DEM resolution. *Earth Surface Processes and Landforms*, 25, 1025–1034. [https://doi.org/10.1002/1096-9837\(200008\)25:9<1025::AID-ESP116>3.0.CO;2-Z](https://doi.org/10.1002/1096-9837(200008)25:9<1025::AID-ESP116>3.0.CO;2-Z)
- Scottish Environmental Protection Agency, SEPA. (2018). Flood risk management strategy. <https://www.sepa.org.uk/environment/water/flooding/flood-risk-management/>
- Scricieiu, A., Rotaru, S., Alexandrescu, B., Catianis, I., Nanu, F., Marchal, R., Pagano, A., & Giordano, R. (2023). Reducing water related risks in the lower danube through nature based solution design: A stakeholder participatory process. In *Natural Assurance Schemes*. Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-25308-9_10
- Seddon, N., Chausson, A., Berry, P., Girardin, C. A. J., Smith, A., & Turner, B. (2020). Understanding the value and limits of nature-based solutions to climate change and other global challenges. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 375(1794), 20190120. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2019.0120>
- Seddon, N., Smith, A., Smith, P., Key, I., Chausson, A., Girardin, C., House, J., Srivastava, S., & Turner, B. (2021). Getting the message right on nature-based solutions to climate change. *Global Change Biology*, 27(8), 1518–1546. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.15513>
- Serra-Sogas, N., Kockel, A., Game, E. T., Possingham, H. P., McGowan, J., Williams, B., Ardron, J., Klein, C., Nicolson, D., & Watts, M. (2013). i User manual MARXAN Marxan version 2.43 and above. <https://pacmara.org/mgph-v2>
- Shao, J., Liu, Z., Ma, G., Zhang, Q., & Wang, J. (2024). Green growth and urban employment: Evaluating the impact of ecosystem conservation on diverse sectors in Yunnan Province, China. *Sustainable Development*, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.316814>
- Sharp, R., Chaplin-Kramer, R., Wood, S., Guerry, A., Tallis, H., Ricketts, T., Nelson, E., Ennaanay, D., Wolny, S., Olwero, N., Vigerstol, K., Pennington, D., Mendoza, G., Aukema, J., Foster, J., Forrest, J., Cameron, D. R., Arkema, K., Lonsdorf, E., & Douglass, J. (2018). *INVEST User's guide*. The Natural Capital Project, Stanford University, University of Minnesota, The Nature Conservancy, and World Wildlife Fund. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32693.78567>
- Sherrouse, B., Semmens, D., & Darius, J. (2020). Techniques and methods 7-C25 social values for ecosystem services, version 4.0 (SoIVES 4.0)—Documentation and user manual.
- Sherrouse, B. C., Semmens, D. J., & Clement, J. M. (2014). An application of social values for ecosystem services (SoIVES) to three national forests in Colorado and Wyoming. *Ecological Indicators*, 36, 68–79. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2013.07.008>
- Smith, P., Knem, J., Calvin, K., Campbell, D., Cherubini, F., Grassi, G., Korotkov, V., Hoang, A. L., Lwasa, S., McElwee, P., Nkonya, E., Saigusa, N., Soussana, J.-F., & Taboada, M. A. (2019). *Interlinkages between desertification, land degradation, food security and GHG fluxes: Synergies, trade-offs and integrated response options table of contents*. IPCC.
- Somarakis, G., Stagakis, S., & Chrysoulakis, N. (2019). *ThinkNature: Nature-based solutions handbook*. European Union. <https://doi.org/10.26225/jerv-w202>
- Tallis, H. T., Ricketts, T., Guerry, A. D., Nelson, D., Wolny, N., Vigerstol, K., Pennington, G., Aukema, J. F., Forrest, J., Cameron, E., Kennedy, C., Verutes, G., Kim, C. K., Guannel, G., Papenfus, M., Toft, J., Marsik, M. J., & Bernhardt, J. (2011). *INVEST 2.0 beta user's guide: Integrated valuation of ecosystem services and tradeoffs*. *Aquaculture*. Stanford University, University of Minnesota, Chinese Academy of Sciences, The Nature Conservancy, World Wildlife Fund, Stockholm Resilience Centre and the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences.
- Tallis, H. T., Ricketts, T., Nelson, E., Ennaanay, D., Wolny, S., Olwero, N., Vigerstol, K., Pennington, D., Mendoza, G., Aukema, J., Foster, J., Forrest, J., Cameron, D., Arkema, K., Lonsdorf, E., & Kennedy, C.

- (2010). *InVEST 1.004 Beta User's guide: Integrated valuation of ecosystem services and tradeoffs*. The natural Capital Project.
- Tanahashi, T. (1978). Health service coverage and its evaluation. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization*, 56(2), 295–303.
- Thames Water. (2020). Thames Water Integrated Water Management Strategy. <https://www.thameswater.co.uk/about-us/responsibility/environment/water-management>
- The LUCI Team. (2019). *LUCI help documentation*. The LUCI Team.
- Thompson, A., Bunds, K., Larson, L., Cutts, B., & Hipp, J. A. (2023). Paying for nature-based solutions: A review of funding and financing mechanisms for ecosystem services and their impacts on social equity. *Sustainable Development*, 31, 1991–2066. <https://doi.org/10.1002/sd.1931>
- Thompson, M. A., Owen, S., Lindsay, J. M., Leonard, G. S., & Cronin, S. J. (2017). Scientist and stakeholder perspectives of transdisciplinary research: Early attitudes, expectations, and tensions. *Environmental Science & Policy*, 74, 30–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2017.04.006>
- Trodahl, M. I., Jackson, B. M., Deslippe, J. R., & Metherell, A. K. (2017). Investigating trade-offs between water quality and agricultural productivity using the land utilisation and capability indicator (LUCI)—A New Zealand application. *Ecosystem Services*, 26, 388–399. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2016.09.002>
- Turney, C., Ausseil, A.-G., & Broadhurst, L. (2020). Urgent need for an integrated policy framework for biodiversity loss and climate change. *Nature ecology & evolution*, 4, 996. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-020-1242-2>
- U.S. EPA, (2019). The benefits and costs of the Clean Air Act from 1990 to 2020. <https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2015-07/documents/summaryreport.pdf>
- United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). (2019). Nature for development: Ecosystem services valuation and policy. <https://www.undp.org/publications/nature-development-ecosystem-services-valuation-and-policy>
- United Nations Environment Assembly–UNEA. (2020). *Resolution adopted by the United Nations environment assembly on 2 march 2022—Nature-based solutions for supporting sustainable development*. UNEA.
- USAID (2016). *Nigeria—Accessibility to EmONC facilities for the states of Ebonyand Kogi*, USAID. http://pdf.usaid.gov/pdf_docs/pa00mdwb.pdf.
- Van Oijstaeijen, W., Van Passel, S., & Cools, J. (2020). Urban green infrastructure: A review on valuation toolkits from an urban planning perspective. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 267, 110603. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2020.110603>
- Veerkamp, C. J., Loreti, M., Benavidez, R., Jackson, B., & Schipper, A. M. (2023). Comparing three spatial modeling tools for assessing urban ecosystem services. *Ecosystem Services*, 59, 101500. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecoser.2022.101500>
- Vigerstol, K. L., & Aukema, J. E. (2011). A comparison of tools for modeling freshwater ecosystem services. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 92(10), 2403–2409. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2011.06.040>
- Villa, F., Ceroni, M., Bagstad, K., Johnson, G., & Krivov, S. (2009). ARIES (Artificial intelligence for ecosystem services): A new tool for ecosystem services assessment, planning, and valuation. *Aries, BioEcon*, 1–10.
- Viti, M., Löwe, R., Sørup, H. J. D., Rasmussen, M., Arnbjerg-Nielsen, K., & McKnight, U. S. (2022). Knowledge gaps and future research needs for assessing the non-market benefits of nature-based solutions and nature-based solution-like strategies. *Science of the Total Environment*, 841, 156636. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.156636>
- Watkin, L. J., Ruangpan, L., Vojinovic, Z., Weesakul, S., & Torres, A. S. (2019). A framework for assessing benefits of implemented nature-based solutions. *Sustainability*, 11, 6788. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11236788>
- Watts, K., Eycott, A. E., Handley, P., Ray, D., Humphrey, J. W., & Quine, C. P. (2010). Targeting and evaluating biodiversity conservation action within fragmented landscapes: An approach based on generic focal species and least-cost networks. *Landscape Ecology*, 25(9), 1305–1318. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-010-9507-9>
- Watts, K., Ray, D., Quine, C., Humphrey, J., & Griffiths, M. (2007). Evaluating biodiversity in fragmented landscapes: Applications of landscape ecology tools.
- Wellmann, T., Andersson, E., Knapp, S., Lausch, A., Palliwoda, J., Priess, J., Scheuer, S., & Haase, D. (2023). Reinforcing nature-based solutions through tools providing social-ecological-technological integration. In *Ambio* (Vol. 52, pp. 489–507). Springer Science and Business Media B. V. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13280-022-01801-4>
- Welsh Government (2018). *Brexit and our land: Securing the future of welsh farming—our response*; Land Management Reform Division: Cardiff, UK; pp. 1–14.
- WHO, UNFPA, & UNICEF and Mailman School of Public Health Averting Maternal Death and Disability. (2009). *Monitoring emergency obstetric care: A handbook*. World Health Organization.
- Winn, JP, Bellamy, CC, & Fisher T. (2018). *EcoServ-GIS: a toolkit for mapping ecosystem services*. *Scottish Natural Heritage Research Report No. 954*. <https://www.ecocolife.org.uk/>
- Yang, Q., Liu, G., Casazza, M., Gonella, F., & Yang, Z. (2021). Three dimensions of biodiversity: New perspectives and methods. *Ecological Indicators*, 130, 108099. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2021.108099>
- Zandebasiri, M., Azadi, H., Shirmardi, H. A., Goujani, H. J., Iranmanesh, Y., Shamsoddini, S., Fakhimi, E., Mokhtarpour, T., Gholipour, Z., & Viira, A. H. (2023). The economic valuation of ecosystem services: Economic value-based Management in a Case Study of protected areas in Iran. *International Journal of Environmental Research*, 17(5), 1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41742-023-00536-8>
- Zhao, M., He, Z., Du, J., Chen, L., Lin, P., & Fang, S. (2019). Assessing the effects of ecological engineering on carbon storage by linking the CA-Markov and InVEST models. *Ecological Indicators*, 98, 29–38. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2018.10.052>

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

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